

THE FIRST TWO WEEKS: SPOTTING AND TREATING FADING PUPPY SYNDROME

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ABSTRACT

Fading Puppy Syndrome (FPS) is a sickness in which apparently healthy newborn dogs suddenly become ill and die during their first two weeks of life. This sickness is caused by the “neonatal triad”. It's a vicious cycle of low blood sugar, low body temperature, and dehydration. FPS may be caused by a variety of factors including sepsis in the neonate, congenital abnormalities, maternal factors (such as mastitis or poor care), and poor environmental control. A change in temperature of the whelping room or inadequate insulation in the kennel is a major cause of infant mortality. Clinical signs are more general and include poor suck, restlessness or a quiet cry, and loss of the righting reflex. Systematic autopsies and complete breeding records are necessary to distinguish FPS from other infectious diseases. This implies that the first 48 hours of life are the most important for a litter's survival.

Fading puppy syndrome is a disease where newborns initially appear healthy at birth but slowly deteriorate and die within the first two weeks of life (Khan et al., 2009). There will be gradual progression of symptoms like tiredness, low body temperature and failure to grow. These symptoms can mask a number of underlying infectious, metabolic or congenital causes (Tal et al., 2021). This vulnerability occurs because a puppy's body is not yet fully developed, and its homeostatic systems are not yet able to cope with environmental or nutritional stressors (Fox, 1965). Hypoglycemia is the most common metabolic risk encountered due to inadequate glucose or liver functions. According to Rodríguez-Trujillo et al. (2025), it is necessary to keep blood glucose levels above a certain level (79.50 mg/dL) for survival because lower levels are often associated with secondary problems such as sepsis. Hypothermia and dehydration are the most important non-infectious causes of death, which are often aggravated by an impaired thermoregulation and fluid balance (Munnich & Kuchenmeister, 2014). These 3 problems influence each other and form the “neonatal triad” which is a dangerous loop that can kill the puppy. Most puppies die in the first

two to three weeks of life. Usually the problem is the mother, lack of help during delivery or poor care of the puppies after birth (Uchańska et al., 2022).

Moreover, “faders” can have multifactorial etiology, from neonatal sepsis and congenital malformations to infectious agents acquired in the immediate perinatal period (Münnich, 2022). Until now, it was thought that puppies that faded were normal at birth, then became ill and died in the first two to three weeks of life. However, failure to thrive was evident from day one, shortly after birth.

A few puppies have prolonged course of illness lasting more than three days or died suddenly without warning. Difficulty in feeding was a common feature in the first week and even where puppies were seen to be attached to a teat shortly before death, postmortem examination revealed empty stomachs and intestines with little content. Abnormal prolonged plaintive crying was not always recorded in the fading puppy group. The literature reported signs of illness associated with fading puppy syndrome included paddling of the limbs while the puppy was in lateral recumbency, gasping, loss of righting reflex, wandering,

restlessness, tetanic-like rigours, slowness of movement, abnormal sleep, maternal rejection, evidence of dehydration, weak sucking, cessation of feeding, periods of apnoea, coma and death. Previously the signs were described as occurring in sequence beginning with a strong healthy puppy which became restless, cried abnormally and gradually passed into a passive terminal phase before death, a course of illness typically lasting 24 to 48 hours (Fox 1966). Although abnormal crying did occur more frequently in the fading group than in those with a known cause of death, significant numbers showed only passive signs of weakness and lassitude before death. A healthy puppy has a shiny coat and a round, plump belly. As you peel it away from the body, the skin should feel warm and stretchy. The puppy is generally happy to sleep 90% of the time showing an active form of sleep pattern and only waking for short periods of regular feeding. Puppies only fuss when they need to begin suckling again. Puppies gain weight every day after birth and by the 10th day their weight is doubled. If this usual look and behavior change, it means that the puppy is ill. One more thing that has been linked to high infant death rates is bad kennel management. The most common problem in breeding kennels was the wide fluctuation of temperature in the whelping area. This was normally down to poor insulation and drafts. Obviously it is difficult to devise a programme of prevention and treatment for a disease or group of diseases of uncertain aetiology. So it is better to think in terms of first reducing overall morbidity and mortality in a kennels and especially if there has been a history of puppy deaths on the premises. It is always worthwhile before making any initial judgments to get details of the last two to three years of breeding history and to assess the management situation in the kennels. An outline of investigation of neonatal mortality in dogs has been provided by Blunden (1987).

In reality, sick neonates presenting at a veterinary practice are usually too far gone for any treatment to be successful. Whatever the cause of neonatal illness, the vulnerable

neonate will soon enter a progressive spiral of hypothermia, hypoglycaemia and dehydration, and any attempted treatment should take that likelihood into account. Liver glycogen stores are rapidly depleted during the first day of life and, with water accounting for 80 per cent of bodyweight and a turnover rate twice that of the adult in the setting of immature kidney function, this leaves the neonate particularly vulnerable to dehydration. Breeders should weigh puppies daily and check for weight gain or loss using a scale that is accurate. If puppies do not gain weight over a 24 hour period or lose weight supplementary feeding should be considered. Low birthweight pups should be identified for extra care. Puppies that lose more than 10 per cent of their birth weight have poor prospects for survival (Wilsman and Van-Sickle 1973). Lactation problems have to be taken into account, eg, mastitis which the pups cannot suck properly and inadequate milk intake due to too large litter size. There needs to be a good supervision of the dam and litter, especially during the first 24 to 48 hours.

Breeders should be encouraged to ensure that their dogs are given booster vaccinations at the correct intervals and dams introduced to their whelping environment at least two weeks before whelping so that maternal antibodies can be boosted and to ensure optimal protection for the puppies from the colostrum within the first 12 to 24 hours. Neonatal infections are often acquired through the umbilicus and use of antiseptic to the umbilicus would be a logical preventive intervention. Antibiotics are of questionable value and should be used only when there is a good indication clinically or from previous postmortem investigations that this is likely to be a cause of illness. In anecdotal experience, antibiotics seem to have little value in treating fading puppies. The phrase 'fading puppy' or FPS can be used loosely and inappropriately but there are a significant numbers of puppies that die without obvious cause in the first week of life. The term 'fading puppy' is not just a catch-all. There is a failure-to-thrive syndrome in puppies which would otherwise

be expected to survive but instead go into rapid decline shortly after birth. Unfortunately clinical signs are non-specific and reflect the immaturity of the canine neonate. Systematic post mortem investigation of litter losses to distinguish between puppies dying of an established cause, such as infection and those without an obvious cause of death. An adequate history in a breeding kennels, including details of past breeding history, clinical histories of the breeding bitches and puppies and recording the results of postmortem investigation, can take time to build up. This may be an expensive process and should be discussed with the breeder at the start of an investigation. What we do know is that the first 24 to 48 hours of life are crucial to the outcome of the litter and good care and supervision during this time is essential.

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